

THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE NUMBER OF FIXED POINTS IN k-PERMUTATIONS

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Abstract

Let S_n be the set of all permutations of an n -element set. We investigate the sequence $a(n, k, j)$, which counts the number of permutations, $\sigma \in S_n$, that have k cycles and j fixed points. We prove that the polynomial associated with $a(n, k, j)$, $1 \leq k \leq n$, has only real zeros for each $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. We improve an asymptotic expansion for Stirling numbers of the first kind; then, we use it to prove the asymptotic normality of the sequence $a(n, k, j)$ in a certain range of the integer k .

1. Introduction

The set of all permutations of n objects is denoted as S_n . Let

$$\hat{s}(n, k) = \{f \in S_n\},$$

where f has k cycles in its decomposition. Then,

$$|\hat{s}(n, k)| = c(n, k) = (-1)^{n+k} s(n, k),$$

where $c(n, k)$ is the signless Stirling number of the first kind, and $s(n, k)$ is the Stirling number of the first kind.

In this paper, the number of permutations $\sigma \in \hat{s}(n, k)$ having j fixed points, $0 \leq j \leq k$, denoted $a(n, k, j)$, is investigated. First, we determine the sequence $a(n, k, j)$, as well as its generating function.

We define the random variable $X_{n,k}$ associated with the sequence $a(n, k, j)$ as

$$\Pr(X_{n,k} = j) = \frac{a(n, k, j)}{c(n, k)}, \quad 0 \leq j \leq k \leq n.$$

The generating function of the sequence $a(n, k, j)$ will help us to find the parameters of the random variable $X_{n,k}$.

Usually, when the generating polynomial, $P_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n a_{n,k}x^k$, associated with a positive sequence, $(a_{n,k})_{k=0}^n$ (where $\sum_{k=0}^n a_{n,k} > 0$), is known to have only negative zeros, a central limit theorem is obtained by proving that the variance

$$\sigma_n^2 = \left(\frac{P_n''(1)}{P_n(1)} + \frac{P_n'(1)}{P_n(1)} - \left(\frac{P_n'(1)}{P_n(1)} \right)^2 \right)$$

grows infinitely with n .

In Section 3, we prove that the polynomial $P(x) = \sum_{j=0}^k a(n, k, j)x^j$ has only real zeros. In Theorem 8, we show that the sequence $a(n, k, j)$ is asymptotically normal by proving that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_n^2 = +\infty,$$

and k satisfies $\frac{k}{\ln n} \rightarrow +\infty$, $k < n - O(n^\alpha)$, with $0 < \alpha < 1$.

Finally, we note that the asymptotic normality of the sequence $a(n, k, j)$ can not be deduced via the theory developed in [14, 15]. This is due to the fact that there is no convenient recursion formula relating the $a(n, k, j)$; hence, the real-rootedness of the polynomial $P(x)$ is obtained by brute force, that is to say, by applying (many times) a classical result due to Schur.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we give all the results that will be needed in this paper. All of this material may be found in [9].

2.1. Permutations

Definition 1. Let c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n be positive integers such that $\sum_{i=1}^n ic_i = n$. A permutation is of type (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) if it contains c_i cycles of length i .

The number of permutations of type (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) is given by the following proposition.

Proposition 1 (Cauchy). *The number of permutations of type $c = (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)$ is given by*

$$P(n, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) = \frac{n!}{c_1! \cdot c_2! \cdot c_3! \cdot \dots \cdot c_n! 1^{c_1} \cdot 2^{c_2} \cdot 3^{c_3} \cdot \dots \cdot n^{c_n}}.$$

In the next proposition, we give an infinite generating function for the sequence $a(n, k, j)$.

Proposition 2 (Cauchy). *Let $P(n, k, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)$ be the number of permutations of type c with k cycles $\left(\sum_{i=1}^n c_i = k\right)$. The infinite generating function of $P(n, k, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)$ is given by*

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(z, u, x_1, x_2, \dots) &= \sum_{n, k, c_1, c_2, \dots \geq 0} \frac{P(n, k, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)}{n!} z^n u^k x_1^{c_1} x_2^{c_2} \dots \\ &= \sum_{n, k, c_1, c_2, \dots \geq 0} \frac{1}{c_1! \cdot c_2! \cdot c_3! \dots 1^{c_1} \cdot 2^{c_2} \cdot 3^{c_3} \dots} z^n u^k x_1^{c_1} x_2^{c_2} \dots \\ &= \exp u \left(x_1 z + x_2 \frac{z^2}{2} + \dots \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $\sum_{n, k, c_1, c_2, \dots \geq 0}$ means the multiple summation $\sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \sum_{c_1=0}^{+\infty} \dots$

Proof. Remembering that

$$P(n, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) = \frac{n!}{c_1! \cdot c_2! \cdot c_3! \dots c_n! 1^{c_1} \cdot 2^{c_2} \cdot 3^{c_3} \dots n^{c_n}},$$

$\sum_{i=1}^n c_i = k$, and $\sum_{i=1}^n i c_i = n$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(z, u, x_1, x_2, \dots) &= \sum_{n, k, c_1, c_2, \dots \geq 0} \frac{P(n, k, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)}{n!} z^n u^k x_1^{c_1} x_2^{c_2} \dots \\ &= \sum_{n, k, c_1, c_2, \dots \geq 0} \frac{z^n u^k x_1^{c_1} x_2^{c_2} \dots}{c_1! \cdot c_2! \cdot c_3! \dots c_n! 1^{c_1} \cdot 2^{c_2} \cdot 3^{c_3} \dots n^{c_n}} \\ &= \sum_{c_1, c_2, \dots \geq 0} \frac{z^{c_1+2c_2+3c_3+\dots} u^{c_1+c_2+c_3+\dots} x_1^{c_1} x_2^{c_2} \dots}{c_1! \cdot c_2! \cdot c_3! \dots c_n! 1^{c_1} \cdot 2^{c_2} \cdot 3^{c_3} \dots n^{c_n}} \\ &= \sum_{c_1, c_2, \dots \geq 0} \frac{z^{c_1+2c_2+3c_3+\dots} u^{c_1+c_2+c_3+\dots} x_1^{c_1} x_2^{c_2} \dots}{c_1! \cdot c_2! \cdot c_3! \dots c_n! 1^{c_1} \cdot 2^{c_2} \cdot 3^{c_3} \dots n^{c_n}} \\ &= \left(\sum_{c_1 \geq 0} \frac{(u x_1 z)^{c_1}}{c_1!} \right) \left(\sum_{c_2 \geq 0} \frac{(u x_2 \frac{z^2}{2})^{c_2}}{c_2!} \right) \left(\sum_{c_3 \geq 0} \frac{(u x_3 \frac{z^3}{3})^{c_3}}{c_3!} \right) \dots \\ &= \exp(u x_1 z) \cdot \exp\left(u x_2 \frac{z^2}{2}\right) \exp\left(u x_3 \frac{z^3}{3}\right) \dots \\ &= \exp u \left(x_1 z + x_2 \frac{z^2}{2} + \dots \right). \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2. A permutation without any fixed point is called a *derangement*.

Let $d(n)$ be the total number of derangements of n objects. Using the inclusion–exclusion principle, one can prove that

$$d(n) = n! \left(1 - \frac{1}{1!} + \frac{1}{2!} - \frac{1}{3!} + \dots + (-1)^n \frac{1}{n!} \right).$$

The number of derangements with k cycles is denoted by $d(n, k)$; this is also the number of permutations with k cycles with a length of at least 2. We have

$$d(n + 1, k) = n(d(n, k) + d(n - 1, k - 1)), \quad n \geq 1, \quad \text{and } d(0, 0) = 1. \quad (1)$$

The proofs of the previous relations may be found in [9].

2.2. Unimodal Log-Concave Sequences

Let us recall the following definitions and facts about unimodal sequences.

Definition 3. A real positive sequence $(a_j)_{j=0}^n$ is said to be *unimodal* if there exist integers k_0 and k_1 , with $k_0 \leq k_1$, such that

$$a_0 \leq a_1 \leq \dots < a_{k_0} = a_{k_0+1} = \dots = a_{k_1} > a_{k_1+1} \geq \dots \geq a_n.$$

The integers j , where $k_0 \leq j \leq k_1$, are the *modes* of the sequence.

Another property stronger than unimodality is described in the following definition.

Definition 4. A positive sequence, $(a_j)_{j=0}^n$, is said to be *log-concave* if

$$a_j^2 \geq a_{j-1}a_{j+1} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq j \leq n - 1.$$

A real sequence, $(a_j)_{j=0}^n$, is said to have *no internal zeros* (NIZ) if $i < j$ and a_i, a_j are non-zero; then, $a_l \neq 0$ for every $l, i \leq l \leq j$. A NIZ log-concave sequence is obviously unimodal; however, the converse is not necessarily true. In fact, the sequence 1, 1, 3, 6, 7, 2, 1 is unimodal but not log-concave. The importance of the NIZ property is illustrated by the following example: the sequence 1, 3, 2, 0, 0, 1 is log-concave but not unimodal.

If inequalities in the log-concavity definition are strict, the sequence is said to be *strongly log-concave* (SLC), and, in this case, it has at most two consecutive modes.

One important consequence of the real-rootedness of a polynomial is given by the following classical result of Newton.

Theorem 1. *If the polynomial $\sum_{j=0}^n a_j x^j$, associated with the sequence $(a_j)_{j=0}^n$, $n \geq 2$, has only real zeros, then*

$$a_j^2 \geq \frac{j+1}{j} \cdot \frac{n-j+1}{n-j} a_{j-1}a_{j+1}, \quad 1 \leq j \leq n - 1. \quad (2)$$

Proof. The result is proved by induction on n . For $n = 2$, the polynomial

$$a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2$$

has real zeros if and only if $\Delta = a_1^2 - 4a_0a_2 \geq 0$. This is Relation (2) for $n = 2$. Suppose now that the statement holds for $(n - 1)$. Let $L(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n a_jx^j$ be a polynomial with only real zeros. By Rolle's theorem, its derivative $L'(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} b_jx^j$ also has only real zeros ($b_j = (j + 1)a_{j+1}$, $0 \leq j \leq n - 1$). Using the induction hypothesis,

$$b_j^2 \geq \frac{j+1}{j} \cdot \frac{n-j}{n-j-1} b_{j-1}b_{j+1}, \quad 1 \leq j \leq n-2,$$

or

$$a_{j+1}^2 \geq \frac{j+2}{j+1} \cdot \frac{n-j}{n-j-1} a_j a_{j+2}, \quad 1 \leq j \leq n-2.$$

The remaining relation, $a_1^2 \geq \frac{2n}{n-1} a_2 a_0$, is obtained by applying the induction hypothesis to $(L^r(x))'$, the derivative of $L^r(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n a_{n-j}x^j$, which is the reciprocal of $L(x)$. □

If the positive sequence $(a_j)_{j=0}^n$, $n \geq 2$, satisfies the hypothesis of the previous theorem, more information about it is supplied by the following corollary.

Corollary 1. *If the sequence $(a_j)_{j=0}^n$ is positive and satisfies the conditions of the previous theorem, then it is SLC, and, in this case, it has a single maximum or a plateau of two elements.*

Proof. We may suppose $a_n = 1$. So,

$$L(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n a_jx^j = \prod_{j=1}^n (x - \alpha_j).$$

Since the coefficients (a_j) are the elementary symmetric functions of α_i , then, necessarily, all α_i are negative. If $a_j = 0$ for one coefficient, then $\alpha_i = 0$ for all $1 \leq i \leq n$, because a_j is the symmetric function of order $(n - j)$ of α_i . Now, we may suppose that $a_i > 0$ for all $1 \leq i \leq n$. Newton's inequalities yield

$$a_j^2 \geq \frac{j+1}{j} \cdot \frac{n-j+1}{n-j} a_{j-1}a_{j+1} > a_{j-1}a_{j+1}, \quad 1 \leq j \leq n-1.$$

The previous inequalities may be written as

$$\frac{a_1}{a_0} > \frac{a_2}{a_1} > \frac{a_3}{a_2} > \dots > \frac{a_n}{a_{n-1}}.$$

Thus, the sequence $(a_j)_{j=0}^n$ is either decreasing (if $1 > \frac{a_1}{a_0}$) or increasing (if $\frac{a_n}{a_{n-1}} > 1$), or there exists an integer l , ($1 \leq l \leq n - 1$), such that

$$\frac{a_1}{a_0} > \frac{a_2}{a_1} > \dots > \frac{a_l}{a_{l-1}} > 1 \geq \frac{a_{l+1}}{a_l} \dots > \frac{a_n}{a_{n-1}}.$$

This means that the sequence is unimodal with mode l . Note that we have at most one integer l such that $\frac{a_{l+1}}{a_l} = 1$. This is the case where we have a plateau of two elements. □

3. The Sequence $a(n, k, j)$

In the following proposition, the value of $a(n, k, j)$ is explicitly given.

Proposition 3. *Let $n \geq k \geq 1$ be positive integers. The number $a(n, k, j)$ of permutations with k cycles that have j fixed points satisfies the following:*

(i) $a(n, k, j) = \binom{n}{j} d(n - j, k - j)$, $0 \leq j \leq k$;

(ii) $\sum_{n, k, j \geq 0} a(n, k, j) v^j u^k \frac{z^n}{n!} = \frac{e^{zu(v-1)}}{(1-z)^u}$;

(iii) $ja(n, k, j) = na(n - 1, k - 1, j - 1)$, $1 \leq j \leq k$;

(iv) $\sum_{j=0}^k a(n, k, j) = c(n, k)$.

Proof. For (i), the number $a(n, k, j)$ is computed as follows: we choose j fixed points among n elements in $\binom{n}{j}$ ways; there remain $(n - j)$ elements, which will be placed into $(k - j)$ cycles that have a length of at least 2. This is performed in $d(n - j, k - j)$ ways. Therefore, the total number is $\binom{n}{j} d(n - j, k - j)$. The generating function of the sequence $a(n, k, j)$ is a consequence of Proposition 2,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n, k, j \geq 0} a(n, k, j) v^j u^k \frac{z^n}{n!} &= \Phi(z, u, v, 1, 1, 1, \dots) \\ &= \exp \left\{ u \left(vz + \frac{z^2}{2} + \dots \right) \right\} \\ &= \exp \left(uvz + u \left(\ln \frac{1}{1-z} - z \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

For (iii), note that for $j \geq 1$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} a(n, k, j) &= \binom{n}{j} d(n - j, k - j) = \frac{n}{j} \binom{n - 1}{j - 1} d(n - j, k - j) \\ &= \frac{n}{j} \binom{n - 1}{j - 1} d(n - 1 - (j - 1), k - 1 - (j - 1)) \\ &= \frac{n}{j} a(n - 1, k - 1, j - 1). \end{aligned}$$

Relation (iv) is obvious. This concludes the proof. □

The aim of the following section is to prove that the polynomial $P(x)$ has only real zeros. The proof is based on two results. The next theorem is due to Schur (a proof of it may be found in [20]). The second one concerns the reality of zeros of the generating polynomial associated with the number of derangements.

Theorem 2 (Schur). *Let $\sum_{k=0}^n a_k x^k$ and $\sum_{k=0}^m c_k x^k$ be two real polynomials having only real zeros. Suppose that all the zeros of one of them are on the same side of the real axis; then, the polynomial $\sum_{k=0}^d k! a_k c_k x^k$ has only real zeros, where $d = \min(n, m)$.*

The second result we need is as follows.

Theorem 3. *For every integer $n \geq 2$, the polynomial $D_n(x) = \sum_{k=1}^n d(n + k, k) x^{k-1}$ has only real zeros.*

Proof. We proceed by induction on n . For $n = 2$, the polynomial reduces to

$$D_2(x) = d(3, 1) + d(4, 2)x = 2 + 3x,$$

and the result holds trivially. Suppose the result holds for $n \geq 2$, and consider

$$D_{n+1}(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} d(n + k + 1, k) x^{k-1}.$$

Using Equation (1), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} D_{n+1}(x) &= \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} (n + k)(d(n + k, k) + d(n + k - 1, k - 1)) x^{k-1} \\ &= ((n + 2)x + n + 1) D_n(x) + x(x + 1) D'_n(x). \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$H_n(x) = (x + 1)x^{n+1} D_n(x).$$

By the induction hypothesis, the polynomial H_n has $2n + 1$ real zeros. By Rolle's theorem, H'_n has $2n$ real zeros; however, $H'_n(x) = x^n D_{n+1}(x)$, and the degree of the polynomial D_{n+1} is n . This means that all the zeros of D_{n+1} are real. \square

The following theorem constitutes the principal result of this section.

Theorem 4. *Let $n \geq k \geq 1$ be two positive integers. Then, the polynomial $P(x)$ has only real zeros.*

Proof. First, suppose $n = k$. Then, $a(n, n, j) = \binom{n}{j} d(n - j, n - j) = 0$ except for $j = n$. Thus,

$$P(x) = \sum_{j=0}^k a(n, k, j)x^j = x^n,$$

and its zeros are real. We know that $d(n, k) = 0$ if $n < 2k$. It follows then that $a(n, k, j) = 0$ for $n - j < 2(k - j)$ or $j < 2k - n$. For this, we consider two cases.

Case 1: $n - k \geq k$. In this case, $a(n, k, j) \neq 0$ for all j , and $0 \leq j \leq k - 1$. So, using Theorem 3, the polynomial

$$D_l(x) = \sum_{j=1}^l d(l + j, j)x^{j-1} = \sum_{j=0}^{l-1} d(l + j + 1, j + 1)x^j$$

has only real zeros for every $l \geq 2$. Theorem 2 can be applied to $D_{n-k}(x)$ and $(x + 1)^{k-1}$ to obtain the polynomial

$$\phi(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \frac{d(n - k + j + 1, j + 1)}{(k - j - 1)!} x^j,$$

which has only real zeros. Its reciprocal polynomial, $\phi_r(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \frac{d(n-j, k-j)}{j!} x^j$, has this property too. Once again, Theorem 2 can be applied to $\phi_r(x)$ and $(x + 1)^n$. The resulting polynomial is $P(x)$, which has only real zeros.

Case 2: $n - k < k$. In this case, the coefficients $a(n, k, j)$ equal 0 for $j < 2k - n$.

The polynomial $P(x) = \sum_{j=0}^k a(n, k, j)x^j$ becomes

$$P(x) = \sum_{j=2k-n}^{k-1} a(n, k, j)x^j.$$

Theorem 2 applied to $D_{n-k}(x)$ and $(x + 1)^{k-1}$ gives the polynomial

$$h(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{n-k-1} \frac{d(n - k + j + 1, j + 1)}{(k - j - 1)!} x^j,$$

which has only real zeros. The same property holds for its reciprocal polynomial

$$h_r(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{n-k-1} \frac{d(2(n-k) - j, n-k-j)}{(2k-n+j)!} x^j.$$

Apply Theorem 2 to $h_r(x)$ and $(x+1)^{2n-2k}$. We obtain the polynomial

$$g(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{n-k-1} \frac{d(2(n-k) - j, n-k-j)}{(2n-2k-j)!(2k-n+j)!} x^j,$$

which has only real zeros. This completes the proof since $P(x) = n!x^{2k-n}g(x)$. \square

The following corollary arises as a direct consequence of the previous theorem.

Corollary 2. *The sequence $(a(n, k, j))_{j=0}^k$ is SLC in j , and it is unimodal with a peak or a plateau with two elements.*

4. A Central Limit Theorem for $a(n, k, j)$

In what follows, we study the distribution of the fixed points in the set of k -permutations. For this, consider the family of random variables $(X_{n,k})_{1 \leq k \leq n}$ on the set $\hat{s}(n, k)$ of k -permutations defined by

$$\Pr(X_{n,k} = j) = \frac{a(n, k, j)}{c(n, k)}, \quad 0 \leq j \leq k.$$

We use a variant of Lindeberg’s theorem to establish the asymptotic normality of the sequence $(a(n, k, j))_j$. Proposition 3 is needed to compute the mean and the variance of the random variable $X_{n,k}$. For a certain range of $k = k(n)$, the variance becomes infinitely large, ensuring the applicability of Lindeberg’s theorem. It is pertinent to recall the relevant definitions.

Definition 5. A positive real sequence $(b(n, k))_{k=0}^n$, with $B_n = \sum_{k=0}^n b(n, k) \neq 0$, is said to *satisfy a central limit theorem* (or is *asymptotically normal*) with mean μ_n and variance σ_n^2 , if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} \left| \sum_{0 \leq k \leq \mu_n + x\sigma_n} \frac{b(n, k)}{B_n} - (2\pi)^{-1/2} \int_{-\infty}^x e^{-\frac{t^2}{2}} dt \right| = 0.$$

The sequence *satisfies a local limit theorem* on $I \subseteq \mathbb{R}$, with mean μ_n and variance σ_n^2 , if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sup_{x \in I} \left| \frac{\sigma_n b(n, \mu_n + x\sigma_n)}{B_n} - (2\pi)^{-1/2} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}} \right| = 0.$$

The following theorem is a consequence of the Lindeberg central limit theorem; for details, see [8].

Theorem 5. *Let $(Q_n)_{n \geq 1}$ be a sequence of real polynomials with only real negative zeros. The sequence of the coefficients of the $(Q_n)_{n \geq 1}$ satisfies a central limit theorem with $\mu_n = \frac{Q'_n(1)}{Q_n(1)}$ and $\sigma_n^2 = \left(\frac{Q''_n(1)}{Q_n(1)} + \frac{Q'_n(1)}{Q_n(1)} - \left(\frac{Q'_n(1)}{Q_n(1)} \right)^2 \right)$ provided that $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sigma_n^2 = +\infty$. If, in addition, the sequence of the coefficients of each Q_n has no internal zeros, then the sequence of the coefficients satisfies a local limit theorem on \mathbb{R} .*

Let us evaluate the mean and the variance of $X_{n,k}$. We have the following.

Proposition 4. *The mean $\mu_{n,k}$ and the variance $\sigma_{n;k}^2$ of the random variable $X_{n,k}$ are given by,*

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{n,k} &= n \frac{c(n-1, k-1)}{c(n, k)} \\ \sigma_{n,k}^2 &= n \frac{c(n-1, k-1)}{c(n, k)} \left(1 + (n-1) \frac{c(n-2, k-2)}{c(n-1, k-1)} - n \frac{c(n-1, k-1)}{c(n, k)} \right) \\ &= \mu_{n,k} (1 + \mu_{n-1, k-1} - \mu_{n;k}). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Consider Assertion (3) of Proposition 3: $ja(n, k, j) = na(n-1, k-1, j-1)$. Summing over j , we obtain

$$\sum_{j=1}^k ja(n, k, j) = \sum_{j=1}^k na(n-1, k-1, j-1) = nc(n-1, k-1);$$

then, we obtain

$$\mu_{n,k} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k ja(n, k, j)}{\sum_{j=0}^k a(n, k, j)} = n \frac{c(n-1, k-1)}{c(n, k)}.$$

Recall that

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{n;k}^2 &= \sum_{j \geq 0} (\mu_{n,k} - j)^2 \Pr(X_{n,k} = j) \\ &= -\mu_{n,k}^2 + \sum_{j \geq 0} j^2 \Pr(X_{n,k} = j). \end{aligned}$$

To evaluate $\sum_{j \geq 1} j^2 a(n, k, j)$, differentiate the generating function in Proposition 3 with respect to v . We obtain

$$\sum_{n, k \geq 0} \left(\sum_{j \geq 1} j a(n, k, j) v^{j-1} \right) u^k \frac{z^n}{n!} = \frac{zue^{zu(v-1)}}{(1-z)^u}.$$

Multiplying by v and differentiating again with respect to v yields

$$\sum_{n, k \geq 0} \left(\sum_{j \geq 1} j^2 a(n, k, j) v^{j-1} \right) u^k \frac{z^n}{n!} = \frac{zue^{zu(v-1)} + z^2 u^2 v e^{zu(v-1)}}{(1-z)^u}.$$

Let $v = 1$ in the previous relation; one has

$$\sum_{n, k \geq 0} \left(\sum_{j \geq 1} j^2 a(n, k, j) \right) u^k \frac{z^n}{n!} = \frac{zu + z^2 u^2}{(1-z)^u}.$$

Equating the coefficients of $u^k \frac{z^n}{n!}$ on both sides gives

$$\sum_{j \geq 1} j^2 a(n, k, j) = nc(n-1, k-1) + n(n-1)c(n-2, k-2).$$

Finally,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{n,k}^2 &= -\mu_{n,k}^2 + \sum_{j \geq 0} j^2 \Pr(X_{n,k} = j) \\ &= -\left(n \frac{c(n-1, k-1)}{c(n, k)} \right)^2 + \frac{nc(n-1, k-1)}{c(n, k)} + \frac{n(n-1)c(n-2, k-2)}{c(n, k)} \\ &= \frac{nc(n-1, k-1)}{c(n, k)} \left(1 - \frac{nc(n-1, k-1)}{c(n, k)} + \frac{(n-1)c(n-2, k-2)}{c(n-1, k-1)} \right) \\ &= \mu_{n,k} (1 - \mu_{n,k} + \mu_{n-1, k-1}). \end{aligned}$$

The proof is concluded. □

In order to apply the preceding theorem, we need explicit equivalents of $\mu_{n,k}$ and $\sigma_{n,k}^2$. To this end, we use an asymptotic expansion of $c(n, k)$ due to Moser and Wyman. When k is small or very large we obtain a degenerate law. For an intermediate value of k we obtain a normal law. We recall the definition of a degenerate law.

Definition 6. A random variable X is *degenerate* if $P(X = a) = 1$ for some real constant a .

In the following theorem, we show that the sequence of random variables $(X_{n,k})$ is degenerate for the extreme values of $k = k(n)$ (small and large values of k , with $n \rightarrow +\infty$). It is noteworthy that convergence in probability is stronger than convergence in distribution. However, if the limit is constant (degenerate) then convergence in distribution implies convergence in probability.

Theorem 6. *The sequence $(X_{n,k})$ of random variables is degenerate in the two following cases.*

- 1) For $k = o(\ln n)$ or $n - o(n^\alpha) \leq k \leq n$, $0 < \alpha < 1/2$, $(X_{n,k})$ converges in probability to a degenerate law at 0.
- 2) If k is large enough and $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{(n-k)^2}{k} = 0$ then $(X_{n,k})$ converges in probability to a degenerate law at n .

Proof. For $k = o(\ln n)$, $c(n, k) \sim \frac{(n-1)!(\ln n + \gamma)^{k-1}}{(k-1)!}$ (see [19]). We deduce that

$$\mu_{n,k} \sim \frac{k}{\ln n} \rightarrow 0.$$

Consequently, $P(X_{n,k} = 0) = (1 + o(1)) \sim 1$. This is expected. Indeed, if k is small and n large enough, there is no place for fixed points. If $n - o(n^\alpha) \leq k$, $0 < \alpha < 1/2$, the asymptotic expansion of $c(n, k)$ in this range is given by (see [19])

$$c(n, k) \sim \binom{n}{k} \left(\frac{k}{2}\right)^{n-k}.$$

Since $n - o(n^\alpha) \leq k$, $0 < \alpha < 1/2$, it follows that $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{(n-k)^2}{k} = 0$; in this case, we have

$$\mu_{n,k} \sim k \left(1 - \frac{1}{k}\right)^{n-k} \rightarrow k.$$

Thus, $P(X_{n,k} = k) = (1 + o(1)) \sim 1$. In this situation, the result is expected; if k is large, almost all cycles have a length of one, that is, they are fixed points. \square

For k such that $\frac{k}{\ln n} \rightarrow +\infty$ as $n \rightarrow +\infty$ and $k \leq n - O(n^\alpha)$, $0 < \alpha < 1$ by the work of Moser and Wyman (see [19, Equation 5.7]) provided the first two terms of a formula are convenient for calculations. More precisely, they gave

$$c(n, k) \simeq \frac{n!u^k}{k!(1 - e^{-u})^n \sqrt{2\pi k K_1}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{k} \left(\frac{K_3}{8K_1^2} - \frac{5K_2^2}{24K_1^3}\right)\right),$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{e^u - 1}{u} &= \frac{n}{k} = \lambda, \\ K_1 &= \lambda(e^u - \lambda), \\ K_2 &= \lambda(2\lambda^2 - (3\lambda + 1)e^u + 2e^{2u}), \\ K_3 &= \lambda(-6\lambda^3 - (12\lambda^2 + 4\lambda + 1)e^u - (11\lambda + 6)e^{2u} + 6e^{3u}). \end{aligned}$$

In the next theorem, employing the same method (and the same notation) as in [19], we give an asymptotic formula for $c(n, k)$ of order three. This result is important on its own, since, in the proof of Theorem 7, we give a complete asymptotic expansion of the Stirling numbers of the first kind (which can be compared with [16, 18, 19, 21, 22]).

Theorem 7 ([19]). *For n and k such that $\frac{k}{\ln n} \rightarrow +\infty$, $n \rightarrow +\infty$ and $k \leq n - O(n^\alpha)$, $0 < \alpha < 1$, we have*

$$c(n, k) = \frac{n!u^k}{k!(1 - e^{-u})^n \sqrt{2\pi k} K_1} \left(1 + \frac{b_1}{k} + \frac{b_2}{k^2} + \frac{b_3}{k^3} + o\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right) \right),$$

where u is the unique positive real root of $\frac{e^u - 1}{u} = \frac{n}{k} = \lambda$, and

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= \frac{K_3}{8K_1^2} - \frac{5K_2^2}{24K_1^3}, \\ b_2 &= \frac{35K_3^2}{384K_1^4} + \frac{7K_2K_4}{48K_1^4} - \frac{K_5}{48K_1^3} - \frac{35K_2^2K_3}{96K_1^5} + \frac{385K_2^4}{1152K_1^6}, \\ b_3 &= \frac{K_7}{384K_1^4} - \frac{20K_2K_6 + 35K_3K_5 + 21K_4^2}{640K_1^5} + \frac{77K_2^2K_5}{384K_1^6} + \frac{77K_2K_3K_4}{128K_1^6} + \frac{385K_3^3}{3072K_1^6} \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{5005K_2^2K_3^2}{3072K_1^7} + \frac{1001K_2^3K_4}{1152K_1^7} \right) + \frac{25025K_2^4K_3}{9216K_1^8} - \frac{85085K_2^6}{82944K_1^9}. \end{aligned}$$

The constants K_i , $1 \leq i \leq 7$, are given by

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 &= \lambda(e^u - \lambda); \\ K_2 &= \lambda(2\lambda^2 - (3\lambda + 1)e^u + 2e^{2u}); \\ K_3 &= \lambda(-6\lambda^3 + (12\lambda^2 + 4\lambda + 1)e^u - (11\lambda + 6)e^{2u} + 6e^{3u}); \\ K_4 &= \lambda\{24\lambda^4 - (60\lambda^3 + 20\lambda^2 + 5\lambda + 1)e^u + (70\lambda^2 + 40\lambda + 14)e^{2u} \\ &\quad - (50\lambda + 36)e^{3u} + 24e^{4u}\}; \\ K_5 &= \lambda\{-120\lambda^5 + (360\lambda^4 + 110\lambda^3 + 30\lambda^2 + 6\lambda + 1)e^u \\ &\quad + (510\lambda^3 + 300\lambda^2 + 109\lambda + 30)e^{2u} + (450\lambda^2 + 345\lambda + 150)e^{3u} \\ &\quad + (274\lambda + 240)e^{4u} + 120e^{5u}\}; \\ K_6 &= \lambda\{720\lambda^6 - (\lambda^5 + 840\lambda^4 + 210\lambda^3 + 42\lambda^2 + 7\lambda + 1)e^u \\ &\quad + (4200\lambda^4 + 2520\lambda^3 + 938\lambda^2 + 266\lambda + 62)e^{2u} \\ &\quad - (4410\lambda^3 + 3542\lambda^2 + 1624\lambda + 540)e^{3u} + (3248\lambda^2 + 3066\lambda + 1560)e^{4u} \\ &\quad - (1764\lambda + 1800)e^{5u} + 760e^{6u}\}; \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_7 = & \lambda \{ -5040\lambda^7 + (20160\lambda^6 + 6720\lambda^5 + 1680\lambda^4 + 336\lambda^3 + 56\lambda^2 + 8\lambda + 1)e^u \\
 & - (38640\lambda^5 + 23520\lambda^4 + 8904\lambda^3 + 2576\lambda^2 + 615\lambda + 126)e^{2u} \\
 & + (47040\lambda^4 + 38976\lambda^3 + 18564\lambda^2 + 6476\lambda + 1806)e^{3u} \\
 & - (40614\lambda^3 + 40376\lambda^2 + 21944\lambda + 8400)e^{4u} + (26264\lambda^2 + 29016\lambda + 16800)e^{5u} \\
 & - (13068\lambda + 15120)e^{6u} + 5040e^{7u} \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Using the generating function

$$\sum_{n \geq k} (-1)^n s(n, k) \frac{z^n}{n!} = \frac{\ln^k(1-z)}{k!},$$

and the Cauchy formula, we obtain

$$s(n, k) = \frac{(-1)^n n!}{2\pi i k!} \int_{\Gamma} \frac{\ln^k(1-z)}{z^{n+1}} dz,$$

where Γ is a circle around the origin, and its radius will be determined later. Let $z = re^{i\theta}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 s(n, k) &= \frac{(-1)^n n!}{2\pi k! r^n} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{\ln^k(1 - re^{i\theta})}{e^{in\theta}} d\theta \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^n n!}{2\pi k! r^n} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \exp(k \ln(\ln(1 - re^{i\theta})) - in\theta) d\theta \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^n n!}{2\pi k! r^n} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \exp(F(\theta)) d\theta,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $F(\theta) = k \ln(\ln(1 - re^{i\theta})) - in\theta$.

In order to find an asymptotic equivalent of $c(n, k)$, we use the saddle point method: the value of the integral is independent of the path of integration. We choose one that passes through (or near) a saddle point z_0 ($F'(z_0) = 0$, $F(z_0) \neq 0$) and along a neighbourhood of z_0 , the imaginary part of F , denoted $\text{Im } F(z)$, is constant. By this choice, the saddle point corresponds to a local maximum in this neighborhood. Thus, the major contribution to the integral essentially comes from the small part of the path containing z_0 . For a detailed discussion of this method, see ([11], Chapter VIII). The calculations are very long as shown by the first few

derivatives of F :

$$\begin{aligned}
 F'(\theta) &= -\frac{ikre^{i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})\ln(1-re^{i\theta})} - in; \\
 F''(\theta) &= k\frac{re^{i\theta}(1-re^{i\theta})\ln(1-re^{i\theta}) + r^2e^{2i\theta}\ln(1-re^{i\theta}) + r^2e^{2i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^2\ln^2(1-re^{i\theta})}; \\
 F^{(3)}(\theta) &= \frac{ikre^{i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})\ln(1-re^{i\theta})} + \frac{3ikr^2e^{2i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^2\ln(1-re^{i\theta})} \\
 &\quad + \frac{3ikr^2e^{2i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^2\ln^2(1-re^{i\theta})} + \frac{2ikr^3e^{3i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^3\ln(1-re^{i\theta})} \\
 &\quad + \frac{3ikr^3e^{3i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^3\ln^3(1-re^{i\theta})} + \frac{2ikr^2e^{3i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^3\ln^3(1-re^{i\theta})}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The fourth derivative of F , with respect to θ , is

$$\begin{aligned}
 F^{(4)}(\theta) &= -\frac{kre^{i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})\ln(1-re^{i\theta})} - \frac{7kr^2e^{2i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^2\ln(1-re^{i\theta})} \\
 &\quad - \frac{7kr^2e^{2i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^2\ln^2(1-re^{i\theta})} - \frac{12kr^3e^{3i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^3\ln(1-re^{i\theta})} \\
 &\quad - \frac{18kr^3e^{3i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^3\ln^2(1-re^{i\theta})} - \frac{12kr^3e^{3i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^3\ln^3(1-re^{i\theta})} \\
 &\quad - \frac{6kr^4e^{4i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^4\ln(1-re^{i\theta})} - \frac{11kr^4e^{4i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^4\ln^2(1-re^{i\theta})} \\
 &\quad - \frac{12kr^4e^{4i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^4\ln^3(1-re^{i\theta})} - \frac{6kr^4e^{4i\theta}}{(1-re^{i\theta})^4\ln^4(1-re^{i\theta})}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The radius r is chosen such that $F'(0) = 0$, or, explicitly,

$$-\frac{kr}{(1-r)\ln(1-r)} = n.$$

The equation $F'(0) = F'(r) = 0$ is equivalent to

$$\frac{e^u - 1}{u} = \frac{n}{k} = \lambda, \text{ with } r = 1 - e^{-u}.$$

The value of $F''(0)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 F''(0) &= k\frac{r(1-r)\ln(1-r) + r^2\ln(1-r) + r^2}{(1-r)^2\ln^2(1-r)} \\
 &= \frac{kr}{(1-r)\ln(1-r)} + \frac{kr^2}{(1-r)^2\ln(1-r)} + \frac{kr^2}{(1-r)^2\ln^2(1-r)} \\
 &= -n + \frac{n^2}{k}\ln(1-r) + \frac{n^2}{k} = -n - \frac{n^2}{k}u + \frac{n^2}{k} = -kK_1.
 \end{aligned}$$

Using the notation of the theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} F^{(3)}(0) &= -\lambda(2\lambda^2 - (3\lambda + 1)e^u + 2e^{2u})ik = -ikK_2; \\ F^{(4)}(0) &= (\lambda(-6\lambda^2 + (12\lambda^2 + 4\lambda + 1)e^u - (11\lambda + 6)e^{2u} + 6e^{3u}))k = kK_3; \\ F^{(5)}(0) &= -ikK_4; \\ &\vdots \end{aligned}$$

We write

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \exp(F(\theta))d\theta &= \int_{-\pi}^{-\epsilon} \exp(F(\theta))d\theta + \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp(F(\theta))d\theta + \int_{\epsilon}^{\pi} \exp(F(\theta))d\theta \\ &= I_1 + I_2 + I_3, \end{aligned}$$

where $\epsilon = \ln k/\sqrt{k}$. We will prove that I_1 and I_3 are negligible, and then, the major contribution to the integral comes from I_2 . The function $|\exp(F(\theta))|$ attains its (unique) maximum at $\theta = 0$. In addition, $\exp(F(\theta))$ is strictly decreasing in the interval $[0, \epsilon]$ since, around $\theta = 0$, F is real and well approximated by $F(0) + \frac{F''(0)}{2}\theta^2$ (recall that $F''(0) < 0$). We have

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Re}\left(e^{F(\theta)}\right) &= \exp\left(\frac{k}{2}\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{4}\ln^2(1-2r\cos(\theta)+r^2)+\arctan^2\left(\frac{-r\sin\theta}{2-r\cos\theta}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\ &\quad \times \cos\left(k\arctan\left(\frac{2\arctan\left(\frac{-r\sin\theta}{2-r\cos\theta}\right)}{\ln^2(1-2r\cos(\theta)+r^2)}\right)-n\theta\right). \end{aligned}$$

Let $\operatorname{Re}(\exp(F(\theta))) = g(\theta)\exp(k\phi(\theta))$. Then,

$$|I_3| \leq \int_{\epsilon}^{\pi} |\exp(F(\theta))|d\theta = \int_{\epsilon}^{\pi} g(\theta)\exp(k\phi(\theta))d\theta,$$

and since F has a *unique* critical point in $[0, \pi]$, the function $g(\theta)\exp(k\phi(\theta))$ is monotonically decreasing in $[\epsilon, \pi]$. An integration by parts yields

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\epsilon}^{\pi} \exp(\operatorname{Re} F(\theta))d\theta &= \int_{\epsilon}^{\pi} g(\theta)\exp(k\phi(\theta))d\theta \\ &= \frac{g(\theta)}{k\phi'(\theta)}\exp(k\phi(\theta))\Big|_{\epsilon}^{\pi} - \frac{1}{k}\int_{\epsilon}^{\pi} \frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{g(\theta)}{\phi'(\theta)}\right)\exp(k\phi(\theta))d\theta \\ &= \frac{g(\pi)}{k\phi'(\pi)}\exp(k\phi(\pi)) - \frac{g(\epsilon)}{k\phi'(\epsilon)}\exp(k\phi(\epsilon)) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{k}\int_{\epsilon}^{\pi} \frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{g(\theta)}{\phi'(\theta)}\right)\exp(k\phi(\theta))d\theta \\ &= O\left(\frac{1}{k}\right), \end{aligned}$$

because all the terms are bounded. It follows that $\int_{\epsilon}^{\pi} \exp(\operatorname{Re} F(\theta))d\theta$ is negligible (as well as $\int_{-\pi}^{-\epsilon} \exp(\operatorname{Re} F(\theta))d\theta$). Thus,

$$s(n, k) \simeq \frac{(-1)^n n!}{2\pi k! r^n} \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp(F(\theta))d\theta. \tag{3}$$

The next step is to evaluate the expression on the right-hand side of Relation (3). For this, expand the function $F(\theta)$ about $\theta = 0$ at any order $l \geq 2$.

We use the notation $a_i = \frac{F^{(i)}(0)}{i!}$. Relation (3) is now

$$\begin{aligned} s(n, k) &\simeq \frac{(-1)^n n!}{2\pi k! r^n} \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp(F(\theta))d\theta \\ &= \frac{(-1)^n n!}{2\pi k! r^n} \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp(F(\theta) - F(0) + F(0)) d\theta \\ &= \frac{(-1)^n n! \exp(F(0))}{2\pi k! r^n} \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp(F(\theta) - F(0)) d\theta. \end{aligned}$$

Since $c(n, k) = (-1)^{n+k} s(n, k)$ and $\exp(F(0)) = (-u)^k$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} c(n, k) &\simeq \frac{n! u^k}{2\pi k! r^n} \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp(F(\theta) - F(0)) d\theta \\ &= \frac{n! u^k}{2\pi k! (1 - e^{-u})^n} \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp\left(\sum_{j=2}^l a_j \theta^j + O(\theta^{l+1})\right) d\theta \\ &= \frac{n! u^k}{2\pi k! (1 - e^{-u})^n} \int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp(a_2 \theta^2) \exp\left(\sum_{j=3}^l a_j \theta^j + O(\theta^{l+1})\right) d\theta \\ &= \frac{n! u^k}{2\pi k! (1 - e^{-u})^n} \left(\int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp(a_2 \theta^2) \left(1 + \sum_{i=1}^l \frac{\left(\sum_{j=3}^l a_j \theta^j\right)^i}{i!} \right) d\theta + O(\theta^{l+1}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

If we rearrange the sum in the last integral and drop the terms of order greater than $l + 1$, we obtain

$$c(n, k) = \frac{n! u^k}{2\pi k! (1 - e^{-u})^n} \left(\int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \exp(a_2 \theta^2) \left(1 + \sum_{j=3}^l c_j \theta^j \right) d\theta + O(\theta^{l+1}) \right),$$

where

$$a_2 = -\frac{kK_1}{2}, \quad c_3 = a_3 = -\frac{ikK_2}{6}, \quad c_4 = a_4 = \frac{kK_3}{24}, \quad c_5 = a_5 = \frac{ikK_4}{120},$$

$$c_6 = a_6 + a_3^2/2 = -\frac{kK_5}{720} - \frac{k^2K_2^2}{72}, \dots$$

Let $y = \sqrt{kK_1}\theta$. The last integral becomes

$$c(n; k) = A \left(\int_{-\sqrt{K_1 \ln k}}^{\sqrt{K_1 \ln k}} e^{-y^2/2} \left(1 - i \frac{K_3}{6\sqrt{k}K_1^{\frac{3}{2}}} y^3 + \frac{K_3}{24kK_1^2} y^4 + \dots \right) dy + O(y^{l+1}) \right),$$

where

$$A = \frac{n!u^k}{\sqrt{kK_1}2\pi k!(1 - e^{-u})^n}.$$

Note that $\int_{-a}^a x^{2i+1}e^{-x^2/2}dx = 0$, and $\int_{\sqrt{K_1 \ln k}}^{+\infty} y^{2j} \exp(-y^2/2)$ is small and may be dropped. Hence, we can complete the bounds of the integral. With $c_{n,k} = c(n, k)$, we obtain

$$c_{n,k} = A \left(\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-y^2/2} \left(1 + \frac{K_3y^4}{24kK_1^2} - \left(\frac{K_5y^6}{720k^2K_1^3} + \frac{K_2^2y^6}{72kK_1^3} \right) + \dots \right) dy + O(y^{l+1}) \right).$$

Using the well-known values of the J_i ,

$$J_i = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^i e^{-x^2/2} dx, \quad J_0 = \sqrt{2\pi}, \quad J_2 = \sqrt{2\pi}, \quad J_4 = 3\sqrt{2\pi}, \dots,$$

we obtain a complete asymptotic formula for $c(n, k)$:

$$c(n, k) = \frac{n!u^k}{k!(1 - e^{-u})^n \sqrt{2\pi k} K_1} \left(\sum_{j=0}^l \frac{b_j}{k^j} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^{l+1}}\right) \right),$$

where

$$b_0 = 1, \quad b_1 = \frac{K_3}{8K_1^2} - \frac{5K_2^2}{24K_1^3}, \quad b_2 = \frac{35K_3^2}{384K_1^4} + \frac{7K_2K_4}{48K_1^4} - \frac{K_5}{48K_1^3} - \frac{35K_2^2K_3}{96K_1^5} + \frac{385K_2^4}{1152K_1^6}, \dots$$

This completes the proof. □

Based on the previous sections, we can now establish the main result of this section.

Theorem 8. *For n and k such that*

$$\frac{k}{\ln n} \rightarrow +\infty, \quad n \rightarrow +\infty, \quad k \leq n - O(n^\alpha), \quad 0 < \alpha < 1,$$

the sequence $a(n, k, j)_{j \geq 0}$ is asymptotically normal with mean

$$\mu_{n,k} \sim ne^{-u},$$

and variance

$$\sigma_{n,k}^2 \sim \frac{k}{\ln n},$$

where u is the unique positive real root of $\frac{e^u - 1}{u} = \frac{n}{k} = \lambda$.

Proof. The polynomial $P(x)$ has only real zeros. So, by Theorem 5 the sequence $a(n, k, j)$ is asymptotically normal, provided that $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \sigma_{n,k} = +\infty$. We have

$$\mu_{n,k} = n \frac{c(n-1, k-1)}{c(n, k)}.$$

Recall that u and v are, respectively, the positive real roots of the equations

$$f(u) = \frac{e^u - 1}{u} = \frac{n}{k} = \lambda \quad \text{and} \quad f(v) = \frac{e^v - 1}{v} = \frac{n-1}{k-1} = \lambda'.$$

Using Theorem 7, we obtain

$$\mu_{n,k} = k \frac{v^{k-1}(1 - e^{-u})^n (kK_1)^{1/2} \left(1 + \frac{b'_1}{k-1} + \frac{b'_2}{(k-1)^2} + \frac{b'_3}{(k-1)^3} + o\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right)\right)}{u^k(1 - e^{-v})^{n-1}((k-1)K'_1)^{1/2} \left(1 + \frac{b_1}{k} + \frac{b_2}{k^2} + \frac{b_3}{k^3} + o\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right)\right)}.$$

To avoid long and tedious calculations, we use only the first terms of the asymptotic formula proved in Theorem 7. This is enough to obtain a central limit theorem.

Let us evaluate $(u - v)$. For this, let

$$f(u) = \frac{e^u - 1}{u} = \frac{n}{k} = \lambda \quad \text{and} \quad f(v) = \frac{e^v - 1}{v} = \frac{n-1}{k-1} = \lambda';$$

$$u = g(\lambda) = f^{-1}(\lambda) \quad \text{and} \quad v = g(\lambda') = f^{-1}(\lambda').$$

The successive derivatives of g are

$$g'(\lambda) = \frac{1}{f'(u)}, \quad g''(\lambda) = -\frac{f''(u)}{f'^3(u)}, \quad g^{(3)}(\lambda) = -\frac{f^{(3)}(u)f'(u) - 3f''(u)}{f'^5(u)}, \dots$$

Then,

$$v = g(\lambda') = g(\lambda) + (\lambda' - \lambda)g'(\lambda) + \frac{(\lambda' - \lambda)^2}{2}g''(\lambda) + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right).$$

We also have

$$\lambda' - \lambda = \frac{n}{k} - \frac{n-1}{k-1} \sim \frac{\lambda-1}{k},$$

and

$$f'(u) = \frac{ue^u - e^u + 1}{u^2}, \quad f''(u) = \frac{u^2e^u - 2ue^u + 2e^u - 2}{u^3}.$$

Then,

$$v = g(\lambda') = g(\lambda) + \frac{\lambda - 1}{k f'(u)} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda - 1}{k} \right)^2 \frac{f''(u)}{f'^3(u)} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right).$$

With $k = \frac{n}{\lambda}$ and $g(\lambda) = u$, we obtain

$$v = u + \frac{\lambda - 1}{k f'(u)} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda - 1}{k} \right)^2 \frac{f''(u)}{f'^3(u)} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right).$$

Replace $f^{(i)}(u)$, $i = 1, 2$, with their values to obtain

$$v = u + \frac{(\lambda - 1)u}{\lambda k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda - 1}{k} \right)^2 \frac{u^2(1 + u\lambda) - 2u(1 + \lambda u) + 2\lambda u}{(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)^3} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right).$$

For the sake of simplicity let

$$v - u = \frac{B_k u}{k} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right),$$

where

$$B_k = \frac{(\lambda - 1)}{\lambda(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)} - \left(\frac{(\lambda - 1)^2}{2k} \right) \frac{u(1 + u\lambda) - 2(1 + \lambda u) + 2\lambda}{(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)^3}.$$

Next, we evaluate $\frac{v^k}{u^k}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{v^k}{u^k} &= \left(1 + \frac{v - u}{u} \right)^k = \exp\left(k \ln\left(1 + \frac{v - u}{u}\right)\right) \\ &= \exp k \left(\frac{B_k}{k} - \frac{B_k^2}{2k^2} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right) \right) \\ &= \exp\left(B_k - \frac{B_k^2}{2k} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right)\right). \end{aligned}$$

The next quantity to compute is

$$\left(\frac{1 - e^{-u}}{1 - e^{-v}} \right)^n = \exp\left\{-n \ln\left(1 - \frac{e^{-v} - e^{-u}}{1 - e^{-u}}\right)\right\}.$$

We have $e^{-v} - e^{-u} = -(v - u)e^{-u} + \frac{(v-u)^2}{2}e^{-u} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right)$. This yields

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1 - e^{-u}}{1 - e^{-v}} \right)^n &= \exp\left\{-n \ln\left(1 + \frac{(v - u)e^{-u}}{1 - e^{-u}} - \frac{(v - u)^2 e^{-u}}{2(1 - e^{-u})} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right)\right)\right\} \\ &= \exp\left\{-n \ln\left(1 + \frac{B_k u e^{-u}}{k(1 - e^{-u})} - \frac{B_k^2 u^2 e^{-u}}{2k^2(1 - e^{-u})} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right)\right)\right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $1 - e^{-u} = \lambda u e^{-u}$ and $n = \lambda k$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1 - e^{-u}}{1 - e^{-v}}\right)^n &= \exp\left\{-\lambda k \ln\left(1 + \frac{B_k}{\lambda k} - \frac{\lambda(\lambda - 1)^2 u}{2k^2(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)^2} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right)\right)\right\} \\ &= \exp\left(-B_k + \frac{\lambda^2(\lambda - 1)^2 u}{2k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)^2}\right) \left(1 + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right)\right). \end{aligned}$$

We note in passing that $O\left(\frac{1}{n^l}\right) = O\left(\frac{1}{k^l}\right)$ for $l \geq 1$. The ratio $\left(\frac{1 + \frac{b'_1}{k-1}}{1 + \frac{b_1}{k}}\right)$ is asymptotically equal to $1 + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right)$. To get an asymptotic equivalent of $\left(\frac{kK_1}{(k-1)K'_1}\right)^{1/2}$, substitute K_1 and K_2 with their values, to obtain:

$$K_\lambda = \left(\frac{kK_1}{(k-1)K'_1}\right)^{1/2} = \exp\left(\frac{1}{2n} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right)\right) \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{e^u - \lambda}{e^v - \lambda'}\right)\right).$$

Let

$$E_\lambda = \left(\frac{e^u - \lambda}{e^v - \lambda'}\right)^{1/2}.$$

From

$$e^u = \lambda u + 1, \quad e^v = \lambda' v + 1, \quad \lambda' - \lambda = \frac{\lambda - 1}{k} + o(1), \quad v - u = \frac{B_k u}{k} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right),$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} E_\lambda &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{\lambda' v - \lambda' + 1}{\lambda u - \lambda + 1}\right)\right) \\ &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \ln\left(1 + \frac{B_k u}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)} + \frac{(\lambda - 1)u}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)} - \frac{(\lambda - 1)}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)}\right)\right) \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Substituting B_k with its value yields

$$\begin{aligned} E_\lambda &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \ln\left(1 + \frac{\lambda(\lambda - 1)u}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)^2} + \frac{(\lambda - 1)u}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)} - \frac{(\lambda - 1)}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)}\right)\right) \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

After expanding $\ln\left(1 + \frac{\lambda(\lambda - 1)u}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)^2} + \dots\right)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} K_\lambda &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda(\lambda - 1)u}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)^2} + \frac{(\lambda - 1)u}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)} - \frac{(\lambda - 1)}{k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)}\right) + \frac{1}{2n}\right) \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Recall that $\mu_{n,k}$ is given by

$$\mu_{n,k} = (1 - e^{-v}) \frac{k}{v} \left(\frac{v}{u}\right)^k \left(\frac{1 - e^{-u}}{1 - e^{-v}}\right)^n \left(\frac{kK_1}{(k-1)K'_1}\right)^{1/2} \frac{\left(1 + \frac{b'_1}{k-1}\right)}{\left(1 + \frac{b_1}{k}\right)} (1 + o(1)).$$

Since $u \sim v$ and $1 - e^{-u} \sim 1 - e^{-v}$, we have

$$\mu_{n,k} \sim (1 - e^{-u}) \frac{k}{u} \left(\frac{v}{u}\right)^k \left(\frac{1 - e^{-u}}{1 - e^{-v}}\right)^n \left(\frac{kK_1}{(k-1)K'_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\left(1 + \frac{b'_1}{k-1}\right)}{\left(1 + \frac{b_1}{k}\right)}. \tag{4}$$

Remembering that $(1 - e^{-u}) = \lambda u e^{-u}$, and replacing each term in Relation (4) with its asymptotic equivalent, we obtain

$$\mu_{n,k} \sim n \exp\left(-u - \frac{\lambda(\lambda - 1)}{2k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)^2} + \frac{(\lambda - 1)u}{2k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)^2} - \frac{(\lambda - 1)}{2k(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)}\right).$$

Keeping just the first term in the previous relation yields $\mu_{n,k} \sim n e^{-u}$ for large n and k in the indicated range. An equivalent value of $\sigma_{n,k}^2$ is deduced from $\mu_{n,k}$ as follows:

$$\sigma_{n,k}^2 = \mu_{n,k} (1 + \mu_{n-1,k-1} - \mu_{n;k}) \sim n e^{-u} (1 + (n - 1)e^{-v} - n e^{-u}).$$

Using the facts that $u \sim v$ and $e^{-v} - e^{-u} \sim (-v + u)e^{-u}$ leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{n,k}^2 &\sim n e^{-u} (1 + (n - 1)e^{-v} - n e^{-u}) \\ &= n e^{-u} (1 - e^{-v} + n(e^{-v} - e^{-u})) \\ &= n e^{-u} (\lambda' v e^{-v} + n(e^{-v} - e^{-u})) \\ &\sim n e^{-u} (\lambda u e^{-u} - n(v - u)e^{-u}). \end{aligned}$$

From $v - u = \frac{B_k}{k} u + O\left(\frac{1}{k^3}\right)$ and $n = \lambda k$, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{n,k}^2 &\sim n e^{-u} (\lambda u e^{-u} - \lambda B_k u e^{-u}) \\ &= n \lambda u e^{-2u} (1 - B_k) \\ &\sim n \lambda u e^{-2u} \left(1 - \frac{(\lambda - 1)}{\lambda(\lambda u - \lambda + 1)}\right) \\ &= k u e^{-2u} \left(\frac{\lambda^2 u - \lambda^2 + 1}{\lambda^2 u - \lambda^2 + \lambda}\right). \end{aligned}$$

For large enough n and k , as in Theorem 8, $\frac{\lambda^2 u - \lambda^2 + 1}{\lambda^2 u - \lambda^2 + \lambda} \sim 1$; hence,

$$\sigma_{n,k}^2 \sim n u \lambda e^{-2u} = k \lambda^2 e^{-2u}.$$

The root u may be obtained by bootstrapping:

$$\lambda = \frac{e^u - 1}{u} \quad \text{implies} \quad u \sim \ln \lambda + \ln(\ln \lambda).$$

Substituting u with $\ln \lambda + \ln(\ln \lambda)$ yields

$$\sigma_{n,k}^2 \sim \frac{n}{\lambda \ln \lambda} = \frac{k}{\ln \lambda} \rightarrow +\infty.$$

The proof is concluded. □

5. Conclusions and Further Questions

The original motivation for this work stemmed from a finding in [17]: when factoring a random n -digit number, the distribution of the number of digits in its prime factors is *almost* the same as the distribution of the cycle lengths in a permutation of n objects. In [6], we further explored the distribution of the exponent of the prime number 2 in the factorization of the integer n , comparing it with the number of fixed points in a k permutation of n objects. Additional instances of such similarities, and intriguing parallels in other combinatorial models, can be found in [1, 12, 13].

There is another subject where a similitude may be observed. Let X be an n -element set. Denote by $T(n, j)$, $0 \leq j \leq n$, the number of topologies one can define on X , and having j open sets, which are singletons. For $n = 2$, we have $T(2, 0) = 1, T(2, 1) = 2, T(2, 2) = 1$. More calculation gives $T(3, 0) = 4, T(3, 1) = 15, T(3, 2) = 9, T(3, 3) = 1$. Despite the challenging determination of this sequence, it seems to be interesting and may have many nice properties. We conjecture that the generating polynomial associated with $(T(n, j))_{j=0}^n$, $n \geq 2$, has only real zeros. A weaker conjecture is the log-concavity of the sequence $(T(n, j))_{j=0}^n$.

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References

[1] R. Arratia, A. D. Barbour and S.Tavaré, Random combinatorial structures and prime factorizations, *Notices Amer. Math. Soc.* **44** (1997), 903-910.

- [2] R. Arratia and S. Desalvo, Completely effective error bounds for Stirling numbers of the first and second kinds via Poisson approximation, *Ann. Comb.* **21** (1) (2017), 1-24.
- [3] M. Balazard, Quelques exemples de suites unimodales en théorie des nombres, *J. Théor. Nombres Bordeaux* **2** (1) (1990), 13-30.
- [4] M. Balazard, H. Delange and J.-L. Nicolas, Sur le nombre de facteurs premiers des entiers, *C. R. Math. Acad. Sci. Paris* **306**, Série **1** (1988), 511-514.
- [5] E. Bender, Central and local theorems applied to asymptotic enumeration, *J. Combin. Theory Ser. A* **15** (1973), 91-111.
- [6] M. Benoumhani, Polynômes à racines négatives et applications combinatoires, Ph.D Thesis, Claude Bernard University, Lyon, 1993.
- [7] E. R. Canfield, Asymptotic normality in binomial type enumeration, Ph.D. Thesis, University of California, San Diego, 1975.
- [8] L. Clark, Central and local limit theorems for excedances by conjugacy class and by derangement, *Integers* **2** (2002), #A 03.
- [9] L. Comtet, *Advanced Combinatorics: The Art of Finite and Infinite Expansions*, Reidel, Dordrecht and Boston 1974.
- [10] H. Delange, On the integers for which $\Omega(n) = k$, *Analytic Number Theory*, proceedings of a conference in honour of P.T. Bateman, Birkhauser, (1990).
- [11] P. Flajolet and R. Sedgewick, *Analytic Combinatorics*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2009.
- [12] K. Ford, Anatomy of integers and random permutations, course notes, available at <https://ford126.web.illinois.edu/Anatomy-lectnotes.pdf>.
- [13] A. Granville and J. Granville, *Prime Suspects: The Anatomy of Integers and Permutations*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, 2019.
- [14] L. H. Harper, Stirling behavior is asymptotically normal, *Ann. Math. Stat.* **38** (1966), 410-414.
- [15] P. Hitczenko and A. Lohss, Probabilistic consequences of some polynomial recurrences, *Random Structures Algorithms*, **53** (4) (2018), 652-666.
- [16] H-K. Hwang, Asymptotic expansions for the Stirling numbers of the first kind, *J. Combin. Theory Ser. A* **71** (2) (1995), 343-351.
- [17] D. E. Knuth and L. Trabb Pardo, Analysis of a simple factorisation algorithm, *Theor. Comp. Sci.* **3** (1976), 321-384.
- [18] G. Louchard, Asymptotics of the Stirling numbers of the first kind revisited: A saddle point approach, *Discrete Math. Theor. Comput. Sci.* **12** (2) (2010), 167-184.
- [19] L. Moser and M. Wyman, Asymptotic development of the Stirling numbers of the first kind, *J. Lond. Math. Soc.* **33** (1958), 133-146.
- [20] G. Pólya and G. Szegó, *Problems and Theorems in Analysis*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1976.
- [21] A. N. Timashev, On asymptotic expansions of Stirling numbers of the first kind, *Discrete Math. Appl.* **8** (5) (1998), 533-544.
- [22] H. Wilf, The asymptotic behavior of the Stirling numbers of the first kind, *J. Combin. Theory Ser. A* **64** (1993), 344-349.